

EDUCATION, HUMAN HEALTH AND SOCIAL ASSISTANCE ACTIVITIES OF THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAIN ACTIVITIES

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Abstract

However, if learning institutions, teachers and politicians want to strengthen lifelong learning capacity, there are good reasons to look more closely at how different approaches to entrepreneurship can contribute in different ways to its promotion and use. There is no privileged context for entrepreneurship in higher education, nor is there a way to teach or learn entrepreneurship, nor is there a common vision of what should be included in concepts such as entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial learning.

Keywords: Romanian mountain activities; mountain statistic; education, human health and social assistance activities

Introduction:

Nestled amidst the picturesque landscapes and majestic peaks, the Romanian mountains not only boast natural beauty but also harbor activities crucial for the well-being and development of the local communities. This article explores the symbiotic relationship between education, human health, and social assistance activities in the Romanian mountain regions, shedding light on the initiatives that contribute to the holistic growth of individuals and communities.

Education Initiatives:

Education stands as the cornerstone for the prosperity of any community, and the Romanian mountains are no exception. The region has witnessed commendable efforts to provide quality education, ensuring that the younger generation has access to opportunities for intellectual growth. Despite the challenges posed by the mountainous terrain, schools and educational institutions have emerged as beacons of knowledge, fostering a sense of curiosity and ambition among the youth.

Initiatives such as scholarship programs, educational outreach, and vocational training contribute to breaking barriers and empowering individuals to pursue their dreams. In the Romanian mountains, where the landscape can sometimes pose challenges for educational access, these initiatives play a crucial role in bridging the gap and ensuring that every child has the chance to learn and thrive.

Human Health and Wellness:

The well-being of mountain communities is intricately linked to human health, and initiatives focusing on healthcare play a pivotal role in ensuring a robust and resilient society. Health centers, clinics, and awareness programs are vital components of the healthcare infrastructure in the Romanian mountains. They not only provide medical assistance but also promote preventive measures and health education.

With the challenges posed by the mountainous geography, health initiatives often incorporate innovative solutions such as mobile clinics and telemedicine to reach remote areas. These efforts contribute to a healthier population, fostering a sense of security and trust within the communities.

Results:

A study conducted in Sweden concluded that, regardless of perspective, entrepreneurship and entrepreneurial learning offer new opportunities to improve learning among students. The study also suggests that any political or scientific initiative must recognize the diversity of entrepreneurship education and choose different approaches depending on what is to be achieved. Talking about a special form of pedagogy may seem difficult

Hoppe, Magnus & Westerberg, Mats & Leffler, Eva. (2017) Educational approaches to entrepreneurship in higher education: A view from the Swedish horizon. *Education and Training*. 59. 751- 767. 10.1108 / ET-12-2016-0177).

The studies of Blenker et al. suggests that entrepreneurship creates new opportunities for wealth creation in society by establishing an integrative space in which the reflective capacity to cope with opportunities can be improved. An integrative framework, which brings together the ideas of entrepreneurial behavior, entrepreneurial university and entrepreneurial learning, can be useful for professors of university management and entrepreneurship (Blenker, Per & Dreisler, Poul & Faergemann, Helle & Kjeldsen, John (2008). for developing entrepreneurship education in a

university context. *International Journal of Entrepreneurship and Small Business - Int J Enterpren Small Bus.* 5. 10.1504 / IJESB.2008.015953).

A study by Hatak & Zhou supports previous theorizing in demonstrating that the mental and physical health of entrepreneurs leads to higher levels of entrepreneurial success and subjective well-being. In addition to their own health, entrepreneurs report higher levels of subjective well-being when their spouse is mentally and physically healthy. No support was found for the hypothesis that a better mental health of the husband would be linked to a greater monetary success in entrepreneurship. This result is contrary to previous research which failed to take both partners into account in a cohabitation dyad. Divergent results for dyadic health effects in terms of monetary success thus have important implications for health and human capital research in entrepreneurship (Volume: 45 issue: 1, page (s): 18-42, Article first published online: August 13 , 2019; Issue published: January 1, 2021, Isabella Hatak, Haibo Zhou).

The research conducted by Prag et al. on a number of 37 studies that analyzed 87 relationships between entrepreneurship and economic results indicate some advantages and disadvantages of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurs create more jobs than large companies, compared to their size, but the quality of jobs created by entrepreneurs is lower. This is due, among other things, to the fact that entrepreneurs hire people with lower

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levels of human capital than other companies. Entrepreneurs pay lower wages, but also offer fewer benefits. However, it seems that entrepreneurs offer their employees other intangible benefits, because their employees are more satisfied with their jobs (less paid and less secure) than the employees of large companies. On the innovation side, entrepreneurs do not spend more on research and development than large companies. They produce fewer patents, fewer new products and fewer technologies. Moreover, the percentage of radical innovations is lower among entrepreneurial firms. However, the efficiency with which innovations are produced seems to be higher and so is the quality of innovations, as measured by the number of patents. Entrepreneurs market innovations to a greater extent, but when adopting innovations, they have a lower score compared to large companies. Additionally, entrepreneurs have higher levels of job satisfaction than employees (Prague, Mirjam & Praag, C. & Versloot, Peter. (2007). What Is the Value of Entrepreneurship? A Review of Recent Research. *Small Business Economics*. 29. 351-382. 10.1007 / s11187-007-9074-x.).

Statistics for Education; human health and social assistance activities (figures 1 and 2) with an average of 8261.64 with a standard error of 4455.942.

At a first analysis, the distribution curve is relatively symmetrically central, and the scores around the average are very concentrated, with the appearance of leptocurticity, although the distribution is unimodal.

Figure 1. Histogram for Education, human health and social assistance activities

Source: Author according to Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

Figura 2. Chart of the Q-Q normal plot distribution for Education, human health and social assistance activities after logarithm

Source: Author according to Eurostat - Business Demography Statistics

Entrepreneurship takes place within the new trends of social policy: active social policies. Innovation is the key element of entrepreneurship, which can help us in the reconstruction of social assistance intervention. However, being perceived as a growth mechanism, it poses to humanity (especially professionals) a set of unknown moral, ethical and political issues. (Jesus, Antonela Spínola. (2016). Social Work and Social Entrepreneurship: A new framework for practice?. March 2016. Conference: 6th European Conference for Social Work Research)

Social Assistance and Community Support:

In the Romanian mountains, where close-knit communities thrive, social assistance activities play a central role in ensuring that no one is left behind. Programs addressing poverty, social inequality, and community development initiatives have been instrumental in creating a support system for residents.

Initiatives ranging from job training programs to community development projects uplift the socio-economic fabric of the region. Social workers and community organizers work hand in hand with residents to identify needs and implement solutions that enhance the overall quality of life.

Conclusion:

Education, human health, and social assistance activities form the bedrock of a thriving and resilient society. In the Romanian mountains, these initiatives not only overcome geographical challenges but also contribute to the preservation of cultural heritage and the sustainable development of communities. As we appreciate the breathtaking landscapes, let us also celebrate the endeavors that nurture minds, care for bodies, and build strong, interconnected communities in the heart of the Romanian mountains.

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